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Impact of Job Satisfaction and School Climate on Teaching Efficiency among Secondary School Teachers in Kebbi State, Nigeria

Ibrahim, Musa

Email: musaibrahim@noun.edu.ng

Tel: +2348062622999

Wodi, Catherine Kekeshi¹

Email: wodicatherine@gmail.com

Tel: +2348063453378

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education National Open University of Nigeria

Abstract

Lack of job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools has been linked with low performance and efficiency, a phenomenon that has been attributed to low academic performance of students. This study therefore, investigated the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school Teachers in Kebbi State. Three research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant. Descriptive survey of ex-post-facto design was adopted for this study. Two hundred and sixty-one teachers (male 135 & female 126) were randomly selected. Three standardized instruments were used for the data collection, these includes; job satisfaction (0.73), school (0.85) and teaching efficiency (0.78) scales. Correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis were used for data analysis. The results revealed that there was significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency ($r = .42, p < .01$). There was significant positive relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency ($r = .74, p < .01$). School climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency ($R^2 = 0.55, F(2,258) = 159.87, p < .01$). The result further revealed that school climate ($\beta = .77, t = 14.70, p < .01$) found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction ($\beta = -.04, t = -.81, p > .05$) had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency. The study therefore concluded that job satisfaction and school climate significantly predicted teaching efficiency. It was recommended that government should provide necessary incentives to arouse the interest of teachers, funding of extra-curricular activities in schools and teachers should be motivated to attend workshop, seminars and training programmes as possible through sponsorship.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, school climate, teaching efficiency

Introduction

Teachers develop skills over time through best experiences shared by others, in-service training and classroom practice. Teachers of all walks of life and subjects have the ability to figure opinions and assist form ideas about humanity, society, life and personal goals. Teachers can also develop students' confines and push their originality. Teaching is a tough career, but it is one where you can make the most impact in another person's life. Teachers are arguably the most important members of our society. They give children purpose, set them up for success as citizens of our world and inspire in them a drive to do well and succeed in life. The children of today are the leaders of tomorrow, and teachers are the critical point that makes a child ready for their future. The reason why teachers matter is that children carry what they are taught at young age throughout the rest of their lives. They will use what they have learned to influence society. Everyone knows that today's youth will become tomorrow's leader, and teachers have the access to educate the youth or the students in their most impressionable years whether in teaching preschool, teaching extracurricular, sports or traditional classes. Teachers have the ability to shape leaders of the future in the best way for society to build positive and inspired future generations and their design society, both on a local or global scale. In reality, teachers have the most important job in the world. Those who have an impact on the children of the society have the power to change lives. Not just for those children themselves but for the lives of all.

Teachers are the ultimate role models for students. The fact that students come into contact with many different types of teachers in their academic career means that more likely than not, there will be a teacher that speaks to them. The teacher-student connection is invaluable for some students, who may otherwise not have that stability. Teachers will stay positive for their students even when things can seem grim. A great teacher always has compassion for their students, understanding of

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their student's personal lives, and appreciation for their academic goals and achievements. Teachers are role model for children to be positive, always try harder, and reach for the Stars. They also expose children to ideas and topics that they might otherwise not have come into contact with. They can expand on interest and push their students to do better. Teachers don't accept failure and therefore, students are more likely to succeed. Teachers know when to push students, when to give a gentle nudge in the right direction, and when to let students figure it out on their own. But they won't let a student give up. Teachers provide guidance to students of all types. Teachers are able to see each child strengths and weakness and can provide assistance and guidance to either get them up to speed or push them higher. They will help to reveal students' best skills and teach valuable life skills as well, such as communication, compassion, presentation, organization, following directions and more. Teachers increase productivity and creative of students and therefore, of future workers.

Job satisfaction is a measure of workers contentedness with their job and can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), effective (or emotional) and behavioral components source. It also refers to a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. It is assessed at both the global level (whether the individual is satisfied with different aspects of the job) Speator, (1997) as cited in Ibrahim (2015) mentioned fourteen (14) list of common facets of job satisfaction. Appreciation, communication, co-workers, fringe, benefits, job conditions, nature of the work, organization, personal growth, policies and procedures, promotion opportunities, recognition, security and supervision. Classroom setting, although not something teachers convey to students, classroom setting creates a place where students can learn. Classroom setting involves knowing the students well and placing them into appropriate learning groups. It also involves having an efficient discipline plan in place that secondary students in Kebbi State can understand. This gives a clear picture of the teacher's expectations and places the emphasis on rewarding good behavior instead of punishment. Classroom setting also deals with the use of time throughout the day. Secondary students in Kebbi State need to be on task with very little down time, for the day to run smoothly. Good classroom setting means planning well and including both physical activity and independent study to Foster good habits among secondary students Kebbi State.

School Climate refers to factors that contribute to the lone in schools, and attitudes of staff and students to ward their schools (Ibrahim, & Awoyemi, 2016). Positive school climate is associated with well managed classrooms and common areas, high and clearly stated expectations concerning individual responsibility, feeling safe at school, and teachers and another supporting staff that consistently acknowledge students and fairly address their behavior (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam, 2023). The size of the school is equally important. In this regard, Ademidara, (2016) examined the impacts of performance appraisal on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment and found out that teacher's employees were greater in smaller organization than in large organizations. Teaching and learning situation in schools seem to be a function of the atmosphere of the school and the productivity of the teachers. School Climate is a set of unique characteristics of a school. These characteristics distinguish one school from another. In one school, the school head, teachers and staff may find pleasure in working together. In another school, it may be discontent among the staff. In one school, staff may appear well organized seem competent exhibit confidence in whatever they do, yet in another school, there may be tension as the school heads loses control (Campbell, 2019). School climate is related to school connectedness because without a positive and welcoming school climate, both students and teachers are unlikely to experience connectedness; the poor conceitedness would have negative effect on teacher's job satisfaction and student's achievement. Job satisfaction of an organization is defined as the ratio of outputs produced by the organization and the resources consumed in the process. Teacher's efficiency is the ratio of output produced by the teachers, here the output refers to the quality and quantity of students produces by the teachers.

Climate has been defined in various ways by authors as the perceived subjective effect of the formal system , the informal styles of managers and other important environmental factor that impact on the attitudes, beliefs, values and motivation of people who work in a particular organization , personality of an organization , the atmosphere of the work place , including a complex mixture of norms , values , expectations, policies and procedures that influence individual and group patterns of behavior (Ibrahim & Abdulsalam, 2023, Spencer, Pelote & Seymour, 2008). The school as an organization has certain intends which it has to achieve, in order to achieve these, the institutional climate of the organization including the school system is very important (Ibrahim, & Ihuoma, 2017). This organization climate refers to the working condition among super ordinates (school heads) and subordinates (teachers) in a bid to achieve the aims and objectives of the school system. In one school the school head, teachers and staff may find pleasure in working together. In another school, it may be discontent among the staff. In one school, staff may appear well organized seem competent and exhibit confidence in whatever they do, yet in another school, there may be tension as the school heads loses control (Ibrahim, & Abdulsalam, 2023; Adamu, 2020). School climate is related to school connectedness because without a positive and welcoming school climate, both students and teachers are unlikely to experience connectedness; the poor conceitedness would have negative effect on teacher's job satisfaction and

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student's achievement (Ibrahim, 2022). Efficiency of an organization is defined as the ratio of outputs produced by the organization and the resources consumed in the process. Teaching efficiency is the ratio of output produced by the teachers, here the output refers to the quality and quality of students produces by the teachers (Ibrahim, 2022).

Climate has been defined in various ways by authors as the perceived subjective effect of the formal system , the informal styles of managers and other important environmental factor that impact on the attitudes , beliefs, values and motivation of people who work in a particular organization , personality of an organization , the atmosphere of the work place , including a complex mixture of norms , values , expectations, policies and procedures that influence individual and group patterns of behavior (Spencer, Pelote & Seymour, 2008). High productivity is the hall mark of growth and development of nations all over the world, the level of efficiency, productivity and the ability of the educational system to achieve its set goals depend on the teacher as reflected in performing their defined roles because teacher are the fulcra upon which the whole educational system revolves (Ibrahim 2015; Eduese, 2006). Teachers have been shown to have an important impact on student achievement and also play a crucial role on educational attainment (Lloyd, Mensch & Clark 2000). Teaching and learning achievement depend on teachers, for there can be no meaningful socio-economic and political development in any society without teachers. Productivity is concerned with the overall effectiveness and efficiency of getting things done. It is essentially a ratio to measure how well an organization converts resources into goods and services. In the school system, teachers' productivity may be measured in terms of their performance. In assessing teachers' performance, qualitative tools such as standardized test scores of students have been used (Schacter & Thum, 2004). Bratton and Gold (2017) opined that grades and test scores do not reflect the quality of instruction because teacher input is not the only factor that influence student's achievement in the school system, other factor that have been identifies to have significant Influence on student's achievement include peer effect, ethnicity, gender, motivation, income as well as family background variables such as house hold environment and parental educational background (Williams, 2016). This suggests that teacher's productivity level may be evaluated in terms of what the teachers control and actually do in the classroom such as teaching effectiveness and classroom performance. Teaching effectiveness has been accepted as a multidimensional construct since it measures a variety of different aspect of teaching (Ford & Walker, 2016).

Lack of job satisfaction among teachers in secondary schools has been linked with low performance and efficiency among secondary school teachers (Ibrahim, 2015), a phenomenon that has been attributed to low academic performance of students. The poor student academic performance in recent times has generated serious condemnation and criticisms among members of the public and various organizations. These people according to Elijah and Frederick (2015) attributed non-performance of students to low morale and apathy on the part of the teachers due to poor incentives. Other people even blamed the teachers as being lazy and unproductive, while many blamed the failure on the irresponsibility of both students and their parents (Ibrahim & Rukkaya, 2019; Bandura & Ahmad 2019). Education as agent of national rebirth and transformation needed to be handled with all seriousness. The expected outcome of most secondary school teachers especially in Kebbi State lack efficiency in discharging their duties in school system. Quality education is required for national growth and development. Hence, this research investigates the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers in Kebbi State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the impact of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers in Kebbi State. Specifically, the study tends to;

1. Investigate the influence of job satisfaction on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
2. Examine the impact of school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
3. Find out the relative contribution of job satisfaction and school climate on teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency on secondary school teacher?
2. Is there any relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency on secondary school teachers?
3. What is the joint influence of school climate, job satisfaction and teaching efficiency on secondary school teacher?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses and were tested at 0.05 level of significant

1. There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher
2. There is no significant relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers
3. School climate and job satisfaction has no significant influence on teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher

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Methodology

The descriptive survey of ex-post-facto design was adopted for this study. This was to ensure the study is devoid of manipulation of the variables in concern. The researcher was interested in knowing the joint contribution and the relationship that exist between independent variables and the dependent variables. The population for this study comprised of all public Secondary School teachers in Kebbi State. As at the time of this study, Kebbi State has a total number of 201 senior secondary schools, with 4083 teachers, (SSMB, 2022). Simple Random Sampling techniques was used to select 10 secondary schools, twenty-six (26) teachers were also randomly selected from nine (9) secondary schools, while twenty-seven (27) teachers were selected from the remaining one (1) school. This is due to the fact that the last school visited by researchers has a total number of twenty-seven (27) teachers, after selection of twenty-six (26) needed, the remaining one insisted to partake in the study. That makes a total number of samples to be two hundred and sixty-one (261) participants. Three standardized instruments were utilized for the study. These include: Job Satisfaction scale (JSS) by developed by Mahmoud, Helen and Ijeoma (2015). This scale has 18 items which are positively worded. These items were given scores of 4, 3, 2, and 1 which range from strongly agreed, agree, disagree and strongly disagree respectively. The sum of this value gives job satisfaction score. The reliability coefficient of the sum of the scale is 0.85. A test retest was carried out using pilot tested method on 10 teachers who were not part of the participants and has a Cronbach Alpha of 0.73. School Climate Scale, the instrument was used to measure the school climate and was developed by Keith (2005). The determination of a school's climate is based on 55 items which made of five-point scoring format of, (1) strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Undecided, (4) Agree (5) strongly Agree. It has reliability coefficient of 0.85. lastly, teaching efficiency scale, the instrument used to measure the participants' teaching efficiency was adapted teaching effectiveness scale which was developed by Emmanuelle (2010), it was used to determine the participants' teaching efficiency, and it was comprised of ten (10) items with scoring format (1) Strongly disagree (2) Disagree (3) Agree (4) Strongly agree It has reliability coefficient of 0.78.

The researchers personally distributed and collected a complete questionnaire from the participants. Permissions were obtained from the principals of the sampled schools after which the researchers with other research assistants administered the questionnaire on the participants. The concept of all the participants was also sought before administration. Maximum return was ensured. It took 3 weeks to administer this instrument. Relationship between the independent variables (Teaching Efficiency) and the dependent variables (job Satisfaction and School Climate) was ascertained using corresponding scores obtained from the variables and tested through Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistics, similarly, data on the predictive ability of the independent variables on the dependent variables was analyzed using multiple regression statistics. More so, the hypotheses were analyzed using ANOVA and T-Test. All analysis was carried out at 0.05 margin of error

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment correlation showing the relationship between satisfactions and teaching efficiency

Variables	Mean	S.D	r	P
Teaching efficiency	26.27	7.26	.42**	<.01
Job satisfaction	17.62	3.54		

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result from table one revealed that job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency ($r = .42$, $p < .01$)

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the Relationship between School Climate and Teaching Efficiency

Variables	Mean	S. D	R	P
Teaching efficiency	26.27	7.26		<.01

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School climate	94.98	20.88	.74**
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It was revealed from table two that school climate has a positive relationship with teaching efficiency ($r = .74, p < .01$).

Hypothesis 3

School climate and job satisfaction has no significant influence on teaching efficiency among secondary school teacher

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the Influence of School Climate and Job Satisfaction on Teaching Efficiency among Secondary School Teachers

Predictors	B	T	P	R	R ²	F	P
School climate	.77	14.70	<.01	0.74	0.55	159.87	<.01
Job satisfaction	-.04	-.81	>.05				

The result from table three shows that school climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency ($R^2 = 0.55, F(2,258) = 159.87, p < .01$). The result further revealed that school climate ($\beta = .77, t = 14.70, p < .01$) found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction ($\beta = -.04, t = -.81, p > .05$) had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis stated that, there is no significance relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The results show that there was significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and teaching efficiency. This result implies that positive job satisfaction significantly relates to increase in teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The null hypothesis is thus rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The result is in line with study of Bandura and Ahmad (2019); Ibrahim (2015), which reported that the degree of employees' involvement in decision making at workplace has an impact on teachers' productivity. Amos (2018) emphasized that job satisfaction, that is, the attitudes and feelings that people has about their jobs, for Armstrong, positive or favorable attitude about the work and the work climate indicate job satisfaction. Brayfield and Crockett (2015) found that teachers with higher levels of job satisfaction have also been reported to have higher levels of teacher enthusiasm and self-efficiency (motivations). These are key factors that affect teachers' well-being and instructional behaviour as well as being influential in students' learning, motivational, and emotional outcomes. Given the important role that motivation plays in improving teachers' performance in the classroom, one of the most important variables that is thought to be linked to teachers' job satisfaction is their efficiency as teachers and how well they teach in the classroom.

The second hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant relationship between school climates and teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers, the result shows that there was significant positive relationship between school climate and teaching efficiency. The result implies that increase in better school climatic condition significantly relates to increase in the level of teaching efficiency and commitment. The null hypothesis is thus rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. The result is in line with studies of Robbins (2019), Almond, (2015), Ibrahim and Awoyemi (2016). Robbins (2019) found that teachers with high sense of belonging to the school system and have more opportunity to participate among stakeholders are reported to have high self-efficiency which translates to high job satisfaction. On the other hand, teachers' perceived disciplinary climate has been reported to negatively impact self-efficiency which in turn translates to low job satisfaction (Bandura & Ahmad 2019; Adewale, 2018).

The third hypothesis stated that school climate and job satisfaction would jointly and independently predict teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. The result revealed that school climate and job satisfaction jointly predicted teaching efficiency. When combined the school climate and job satisfaction accounted for 55% of the change observed in the teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers. This revealed that the collective presence of school climate and job satisfaction has significant influence on the teaching efficiency. The result further revealed that school climate found to be significant independent predictor of teaching efficiency among secondary school teachers while job satisfaction had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency. The hypothesis is therefore corroborates the studies by Amos, (2018). Adeyemi, (2015) connotes 'the beliefs that teachers have of their ability to enact certain teaching behaviour that influences students' educational outcomes, such as achievement, interest, and motivation'

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Conclusion

From the result of the findings, it was therefore concluded that job satisfaction had significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency among teachers sampled. Also, school climate had a significant positive relationship with teaching efficiency. Apparently, there was a joint contribution of job satisfaction and school climate on the teaching efficiency among teachers, whereas independently on school climate predicted teaching efficiency while job satisfaction had no significant independent prediction on teaching efficiency.

Recommendations

In order to positively overhaul, remove drastically alleviate the problems enumerated in the study, with a view to improve teachers' efficiency and raise the standard of education, the following recommendations are offered.

1. There should be adequate school plants. This includes school buildings, classrooms, laboratories, libraries, vocational workshops, furniture, laboratory equipment, instructional materials, play grounds etc. the Kebbi State government should provide the above named materials and facilities to meet the ever-growing students population
2. The Government should provide necessary incentives to arouse the interest of teachers in the teaching profession. Incentives like regular promotion, employment of experienced and qualify teachers, increment in salary and emoluments and opportunity for professional advancement to mention but a few
3. Funding of extra-curricular activities in the school. This will help arouse students' interest in schooling and thus change their negative activities in school. The literary and debating societies, jet clubs, vocational clubs, drama and cultural society, young farmers' club, boys and girls brigades, boys scout and girls guilds should be well funded by the government in our schools, to keep the students busy and prevent unwholesome activities such as truancy, cultism, rioting and hooliganism among the students
4. In order to encourage and motivate teachers to be more effective, it is suggested that the government, principals and parents' teachers' association (PTA) should constitute "Best Teacher Award" in our schools.
5. Teacher should be motivated to attend as many workshop and training programmes as possible through sponsorship. This will go a long way in improving and imparting better and in-depth knowledge in their subjects.
6. Merit promotion schemes for teachers may be introduced and implemented systematically, periodically and scientifically. This measure naturally motivates teachers to involve themselves actively in publishing books and articles besides research activities. Because education is the best legacy any parent can give to their children

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